

LAP TRIPS: Learning Activity Package in Traversing Responsive and Improved Psychosocial-Mental Support

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Abstract

Addressing psychosocial-mental (PSM) issues among Filipino students remains a challenge due to a lack of licensed guidance counselors, limited mental health resources, and teacher technical knowledge. This study focused on crafting the Learning Activity Package in Traversing Responsive and Improved Psychosocial-Mental Support (LAP TRIPS), a structured intervention tool to equip teachers to support students' psychosocial-mental health needs. The study employed a multi-phase developmental process involving needs assessment, content design,

expert review, and revision for crafting the learning activity package. A descriptive quantitative method was utilized for the needs assessment, which served as the baseline data for this study. The final output includes teacher-focused modules and student-centered activities. This research serves as an underpinning for teacher capacity-building on necessary abilities to recognize psychosocial-mental issues and intercede more effectively to close the gap between what is deemed to be needed support and actual help-seeking behaviors.

Keywords: *Mental Health Support, Psychosocial-mental issue, learning activity package (LAP), descriptive quantitative design*

INTRODUCTION

Mental health is a growing concern in the Philippines, especially in education. The Mental Health Law and the Department of Education's (DepEd) MATATAG agenda emphasizes the need for mental health support for both learners and educators. Despite these initiatives, mental health challenges persist. According to the World Health Organization (2015), 10–15% of Filipino children experience mental health issues, highlighting the urgency for effective interventions.

In Calamba City, the situation is compounded by a shortage of guidance counselors, leaving many students with psychosocial-mental (PSM) concerns underserved. Additionally, teachers report limited skills and confidence in addressing these issues, further widening the gap in mental health support (Hechanova et al., 2022).

This study focused on crafting the Learning Activity Package in Traversing Responsive and Improved Psychosocial-Mental Support (LAP TRIPS), a structured intervention tool designed to empower teachers in supporting students' psychosocial-mental needs. This initiative aims to address the challenges identified within the local context by equipping educators with practical, culturally sensitive tools.

The primary objective of this study was to develop and refine the LAP TRIPS through a systematic and participatory process, ensuring its relevance and applicability in Filipino classrooms.

Research Question

This study aims to develop a learning activity package that will address the psychosocial-mental needs of the students. Specifically, it aims to answer the following question.

1. What is the level of psychosocial well-being of students?
2. What is the perceived level of psychosocial-mental health of the students in relation to:
 - a. Self
 - b. Others
3. What is the level of knowledge and preparedness of teachers in identifying and managing students' psychosocial-mental issues?
4. What learning activity package can be developed for students to address their psychosocial-mental concerns, designed to be effectively administered by teachers with limited expertise in this field?

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The research was conducted among 90 secondary teachers and 1554 students in Cluster 5 in the Department of Education Schools Division of Calamba City. The survey is a precursor in the crafting of the Learning Activity Package (LAP) in Traversing Responsive and Improved Psychosocial-Mental Support (TRIPS).

Researcher-made survey questionnaires were used to serve as the baseline data for this research. The aim of the first questionnaire is to measure the psychosocial wellbeing of the students. The second data came from psychosocial-mental well-being of the students in relation to self and others. The last questionnaire was administered to the teachers to measure the level of their knowledge and preparedness in handling the student's psychosocial concerns.

The LAP's development underwent rigorous validation by experts to ensure its alignment to the psychosocial-mental needs of the students. The study is limited to the preparation stage of the LAP. It focused on developing a learning activity package that will be utilized by the teachers who have limited knowledge in handling these concerns.

Framework

The conceptual framework illustrates the interplay between students' psychosocial wellbeing and teachers' knowledge and preparedness in addressing related concerns. These two variables served as the building blocks in developing interventions aimed at addressing the psychosocial-mental needs of the learners.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The framework highlights the influence of these three elements and how it served as a guide in the creation of a learning activity package designed to equip teachers with effective strategies to support students.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research method utilized, the study's participants, the research tool, the process, and the statistical analyses performed on the study's data.

Research Design

The first part of the study used a descriptive quantitative design to gather the baseline data for the development of a learning activity package. Surveys were conducted to 1554 High School students and 90 Secondary teachers.

For the second part of the study, a need-based intervention research method was utilized. The first part where surveys were conducted is classified as Phase 1 which focused on needs assessment. Phase 2 is the content design which has the key components of adopted assessment tools, student activities and reflection tools. This is followed by Phase 3 which is the expert validation and Phase 4 is the revision and finalization.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this research were students and teachers from Cluster 5. Separate questionnaires were given to the two groups of respondents.

The participants were selected using purposive sampling. A total of one thousand five hundred fifty-four (1554) students and ninety (90) teachers were selected and participated in the study.

Research Instrument

Pre-survey researcher-made questionnaires were administered to students and teachers. Researchers administered three sets of questionnaires. The first questionnaire measured the psychosocial wellbeing of the students using a 5-point Likert Scale. The second questionnaire measured the student's level of psychosocial-mental health, using a 4-point Likert Scale. The last questionnaire measured the teachers' knowledge and preparedness in dealing with students' mental health concerns. These three sets of questionnaires underwent various validations that ensured their validity.

Data Gathering

Data collection in Cluster 5 involved two respondent groups: students and teachers. The pre-survey questionnaire served as baseline data for developing a learning activity package. The researcher administered two sets of questionnaires to students. These two questionnaires focused on their psychosocial well-being and mental health. To measure teacher's knowledge and preparedness in handling students' mental health issues, another set of questionnaires was administered by the researcher.

Using Cluster 5 as the pilot was crucial for identifying key psychosocial issues affecting the students. The dataset offers insights into student well-being and teacher preparedness in going towards the development of the learning activity package. This structured approach ensures that interventions work towards whatever needs are identified, promoting deeper psychological dynamics in the Philippine system of education.

Statistical Treatment

For this study, the researcher employed mean/average as the core statistical treatment to pool responses in questionnaire from students and teachers. As such, it was computed to determine the central tendency

which can help in assessing the overall trends of responses toward aspects of psychosocial-mental wellbeing among students as well as preparedness from the side of teachers for tackling mental health issues. The mean was used to find out the average level of each key variable being measured in this study.

Research Ethics

The participants of the pre-survey were provided with consent. Confidentiality was emphasized to reassure respondents that their identities would remain undisclosed and that their responses would be used exclusively for research purposes.

III. RESULTS

This part presents the interpretation and analysis of data gathered to discuss the answers to the research problems of the study.

Table 1. Pagsusuri sa Sikososyal ng Mag-aaral

Pahayag	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Mayroon akong mapagkakatiwalaang guro at kamag-aral na bukas upang lapitan at sabihan tungkol sa aking iniisip at nararamdaman.	4.58	Labis na sumasangayon
Binabahagi ko ang aking mga iniisip at nararamdaman sa aking mga kamag-aral, guro, kaibigan, mga magulang o tagapangalaga nang walang alinlangan	3.42	Sumasangayon

The students seldom share their feelings with teachers and classmates despite perceiving them as supportive as supported by research, due to factors such as power imbalances, lack of engagement (Ibrahim & Zaatari, 2020), and insufficient supportive relationships (Garcia-Martinez et al., 2021).

Figure 1. Sanhi o Dahilan ng Pagkalungkot

The result revealed that students' loneliness is attributed to their excessive use of technology. Studies suggest that the reason for this is that it could lead to addiction, which may replace real social interactions (Zhang, 2023)

Table 2. Teacher's Knowledge and Preparedness

Indikeytor	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Madali kong makita at maramdaman ang mga palatandaan ng isyung mental at sikolohikal batay sa mga negatibong emosyon ng mag-aaral.	3.06	Katamtaman
May mekanismo akong sinusunod para maanalisa ang mga negatibong emosyong Ipinakikita	2.80	Katamtaman
May mga pantulong na kagamitang pagtuturo akong ginagamit bilang interbensyon sa isyung ito.	2.82	Katamtaman
Epektibo at mabilis ang mga interbensyon ko na ginagamit sa pagtugon sa pangangailangan ng mag-aaral	2.97	Katamtaman
Mayroong programa ang paaralan para matugunan ang mga isyung mental at sikososyal ng mag-aaral.	3.13	Katamtaman
OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	2.96	

The table shows that many teachers are aware of students' behavioral issues, but a significant number lack awareness of specific mental health issues and do not pay attention to these areas (Pokharel & Adhikari, 2020).

IV. DISCUSSION

The data shows that the pupils generally trust teachers and friends (4.58) but do not want to pour their hearts out concerning their emotions (3.42). This reflects that even though the students feel cared for, power and content imbalances or lack of relations may make them less likely to open. Moreover, the frequent usage of gadgets hampers socializing in real life and even causes loneliness (Zhang, 2023).

Teachers indicate some knowledge of identifying emotional struggles (3.06) and apply interventions to some degree (2.82) but do not always believe their efforts are practical (2.97). Overall, a score of 2.96 indicates that teachers possess some knowledge, but training and mental health resources to address students' needs are likely areas of improvement.

The development of the learning activity package was guided by the insights gained from the pilot data collected in Cluster 5. The package includes three key components: psychosocial adjustment needs, social relations, and mental health support. Each part was designed to address specific challenges identified during the data collection phase, ensuring a holistic approach to fostering students' psychosocial-mental well-being. This package is focused on the emotional resilience of students, strengthening social connections, and providing necessary resources for mental health awareness and intervention within the educational setting.

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